

PRACH Signal Design and Detection for LEO Satellite Systems with Imperfect UE Positioning

Màrius Caus, Musbah Shaat

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya-CERCA (CTTC-CERCA), Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain

Abstract—This paper investigates a novel physical random access channel (PRACH) signal design and detection scheme tailored to low Earth orbit (LEO) satellite systems operating at the Ka band, particularly in presence of user positioning errors. The primary aim is to guarantee the initial access despite substantial time and carrier frequency offsets are experienced by the received preamble. To enable reliable detection, a well-suited preamble structure is crucial. To that end, one viable approach involves the use of a preamble crafted by concatenating a single root Zadoff Chu (ZC) sequence with different cyclic shifts. Building upon this notion, we propose an innovative preamble design that interleaves the redundancy blocks with the ZC sequences, thereby enhancing the performance of the detector. Numerical evaluations show that the proposed scheme has significantly lower missed detection probability (MDP) compared to existing solutions that transmit the whole cyclic prefix (CP) block ahead of the sequence.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is widely acknowledged that non-terrestrial networks (NTN) are poised to play a crucial role in the delivery of 5G services, particularly in regions where technical challenges and economic considerations render traditional terrestrial networks (TN) impractical or unprofitable. The basic idea is to integrate NTN into the 3GPP ecosystem. To maximize the synergies with 5G TN, the approach followed by 3GPP is to adopt the new radio (NR) air interface over terrestrial and non-terrestrial links. In this regard, following Release 15 and 16 study items, the NR-based NTN component has been included in the technical specifications of Release 17. The focus is on direct access and transparent payload architectures with frequency division duplexing (FDD) systems. It is worth remarking that the specifications of NTN are limited to deployments in the frequency range 1 (FR1), i.e., S band in particular [1]. To simplify the adaptations to consider 5G-NTN, the satellite ephemeris are carried out in system information blocks and the user equipment (UE) is equipped with a global navigation satellite service (GNSS) receiver. Accordingly, most of the standardized procedures can be reused in NTN if the UE is aware of its position as well as the trajectory of the serving satellite [2]. The followed approach involves an open loop mechanism where the UE autonomously pre-compensates for both the instantaneous Doppler effects as well as the round trip time (RTT) delay.

In the pursuit of enhancing 5G systems over satellite, this paper challenges the assumptions made in Release 17. More precisely, the objective is to investigate the necessary adaptations required by the random access (RA) procedure to operate in frequency range 2 (FR2) when the GNSS service is

not available. The focus will be particularly directed towards the Ka band. Remarkably, the GNSS independent operation is an enhancement that will be investigated in Release 19 [3]. In the absence of GNSS information, the UE cannot accurately pre-compensate the time offset (TO) and the carrier frequency offset (CFO). The immediate consequence is a significant challenge encountered in the initial phase of the RA procedure. At this stage, the received physical random access channel (PRACH) signal will be misaligned in time and frequency, by values that are not tolerated by the standard. To relax the requirements, alternative positioning methods other than GNSS should be explored. As highlighted in [4], communications from low Earth orbit (LEO) constellations can be used to assist the RA procedure. The idea is to estimate the UE position by tracking the synchronization signal block (SSB). The results presented in [4] show that the positioning accuracy depends on the elevation angle, the number of SSBs that are processed, and the number of visible satellites. Considering the case of single LEO satellite, the positioning error could be in the order of several Kms. Therefore, the PRACH signal detector should be robust to large TO and CFO values.

Building upon previous research findings, one can summarize that achieving initial uplink synchronization hinges on specific conditions: the TO must be shorter than the cyclic prefix (CP), and the CFO should not exceed half the subcarrier spacing (SCS). From the Doppler curve derived in [5], one can infer that the maximum frequency uncertainty manifests around the sub-satellite point at high elevation angles. Similarly, focusing on timing considerations, the maximum temporal uncertainty arises at the edge of the coverage area at low elevation angles. The paper first contribution lies in assessing the suitability of the legacy RA procedure to handle the TO and the CFO values associated with positioning errors. Through rigorous analysis, we show that the preamble formats outlined in FR2 must be enhanced to support higher delays.

Within the existing literature, various preamble designs have been proposed to facilitate the estimation of large delays [6]–[9]. These studies share a common approach, wherein the burst configuration entails extending the CP, the preamble sequence and the guard interval (GI) to accommodate the maximum delay. Typically, the preamble is constructed by cascading multiple identical Zadoff-Chu (ZC) sequences [6]. However, a challenge arises when the RTT exceeds the duration of a single replica, making it difficult to discern the boundaries between the CP and the preamble sequence. Consequently, only fractional delays can be accurately estimated. To overcome this

Fig. 1: Geographic location uncertainty

issue, one viable approach involves concatenating a single root ZC sequence with various cyclic shifts [7]. With the objective of increasing the robustness to the CFO, the extended sequence can be alternatively generated by concatenating different root ZC sequences [8], [9].

Among the possible solutions, in this paper, we favor the design principles described in [7]. This approach demonstrates efficacy in estimating large RTT delays, while reusing the least root ZC sequences to generate the preamble set. Notably, addressing the CFO does not necessitate resorting to complex solutions. Rather, we leverage on the flexibility offered by the standard. More precisely, among the SCS values specified in [10], we can judiciously select the most suitable configuration tailored to accommodate the maximum CFO. As a further enhancement, we propose a novel preamble design that is based on interleaving the redundancy blocks with the ZC sequences, diverging from the conventional approach of transmitting the entire CP block ahead of the sequence. This modification serves to enhance the detector performance when the received preamble is affected by large TO and CFO values. Interestingly, this scenario mirrors the challenges encountered in LEO satellite systems operating at the Ka band, especially with imperfect UE positioning.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we describe the scenario and analyse the limitations of standardized preamble formats. The new preamble design is described in III. In Sections IV and V, we describe the estimation of fractional and integer delays, respectively. The numerical results are provided in Section VI. Finally, section VII draws the conclusions.

II. SCENARIO DEFINITION

In the scenario under study, the network supports direct connectivity between the UEs and the satellites. We consider a LEO constellation deployment with an altitude of 600km. It is assumed that a full gNB is on-board the satellites. Furthermore, UEs are assumed to possess the capability to autonomously pre-compensate for TO and CFO values of the satellite service link. This is achieved through leveraging the UE's coordinates in conjunction with the satellite ephemeris

TABLE I: Differential delay and Doppler frequency shift in LEO constellations at 600 km altitude

Elevation	30°	50°	70°	90°
$R_e = 1\text{km}$				
Delay (μs)	± 2.89	± 2.14	± 1.14	± 0.003
Doppler (ppm)	± 0.023	± 0.033	± 0.04	± 0.042
$R_e = 2.5\text{km}$				
Delay (μs)	± 7.22	± 5.37	± 2.87	± 0.019
Doppler (ppm)	± 0.058	± 0.082	± 0.099	± 0.1
$R_e = 5\text{km}$				
Delay (μs)	± 14.46	± 10.76	± 5.77	± 0.076
Doppler (ppm)	± 0.12	± 0.16	± 0.19	± 0.21

information. However, in the absence of GNSS, positioning errors are inevitable. Consequently, the UE may fail to accurately compute the RTT delay and the Doppler frequency shift. As Figure 1 shows, the UE could be in any position inside a circular uncertainty region. The radius R_e determines the maximum uncertainty while R_E denotes the Earth radius. The reference point (RP) is the center of the region, which corresponds to the true coordinates. The highest differential Doppler (delay) with respect to the RP is observed along the curve that is parallel (perpendicular) to the ground track.

A. Structure of the PRACH burst

Using the model derived in [5], we have gathered in Table I, the maximum differential delay and Doppler frequency shift values considering the worst case, which is observed at the edges of the uncertainty region. The values are provided for different elevation angles measured at the center of the region. Since the RTT delay and the Doppler frequency shift could be either underestimated or overestimated, we use the mathematical symbol \pm to indicate that the differential values may take positive or negative values.

The uplink TO that affects the preamble reception can be computed as

$$\delta_t = 2t_D + T_S, \quad (1)$$

where t_D denotes the differential delay and T_S is the time shift parameter. As the standard is not prepared to handle a negative time misalignment, the time shift T_S is applied at transmission to ensure that δ_t always takes positive values. This prevents the PRACH signal from interfering already synchronized UEs in previous slots. The GI of the PRACH signal serves to absorb positive offsets and avoid the interference to subsequent slots. A practical implementation consists in setting the time shift according to $T_S = T_{CP}/2$, where T_{CP} denotes the CP duration. To counteract all possible delays, the CP has to be dimensioned as $T_{CP} > 4|t_{D,MAX}|$. In notation terms, $t_{D,MAX}$ refers to the maximum differential delay, which is observed at the minimum elevation angle. From here onwards, unless otherwise stated, we assume that the minimum elevation angle is 30°.

The uplink CFO is the combined effect of the differential Doppler frequency shift and the downlink synchronization accuracy. In compliance with the guidelines outlined in [11], the UE is considered to maintain the modulated carrier frequency

Fig. 2: Structure of the PRACH burst

within an accuracy of 0.1ppm. Accordingly, the uplink CFO for stationary users can be formulated as

$$\delta_f = ((1 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-6})(1 + f_D \times 10^{-6})^2 \times f_c - f_c), \quad (2)$$

where f_D is the differential Doppler expressed in ppm and f_c is the carrier frequency. The frequency misalignment could be either positive or negative. To protect adjacent resource blocks, guard bands (GBs) are added to the edges of the PRACH signal.

The proposed structure is depicted in Figure 2. By T_S , T_{PRACH} and T_G , we denote the magnitude of the shift, the duration of the PRACH signal and the duration of the GI, respectively. It should be underlined that the part of the spectrum that remains unused and T_G are specified in the standard. Note that the time shift mechanism can be implemented by adding a zero padding block at the beginning of the burst.

B. NR random access procedure

To analyze the suitability of the NR preamble formats to handle the TO and the CFO formulated in (1) and (2), respectively, the format C2 has been selected as it transmits the largest CP block [10]. With this format, the CP duration is equal to $T_{CP} = 66.66 \times 2^{-\mu} \mu s$ when the SCS is $\Delta_f = 15 \times 2^\mu \text{KHz}$. In this work, we focus the attention on $\mu = 0, 1, 2$.

Considering the preamble format C2, we analyze the positioning errors that are tolerated by the RA procedure in LEO satellite systems that operate at the Ka band. It is resolved that the network can handle a given positioning error, if the corresponding TO and CFO satisfy, $\delta_t \leq T_{CP}$ and $\delta_f \leq 0.5\Delta_f$, respectively. Accordingly, as Δ_f increases, the system becomes more robust to the CFO and more sensitive to the TO. The result of the analysis yields the uncertainty region within which the preamble C2 can effectively work in the LEO constellation deployment. This uncertainty region's radius, denoted as R_ϵ^{C2} , is provided in Table II for different elevation angles.

Based on the values gathered in Table II, it becomes feasible to identify which configurations need to be enhanced. The criterion is as follows: for a given uncertainty region R_ϵ and subcarrier spacing (SCS) Δ_f , reliable preamble detection is assured only if $R_\epsilon \leq R_\epsilon^{C2}$ holds true across all elevation

TABLE II: Uncertainty region supported by the preamble C2 at the Ka band and in LEO constellations at 600km altitude

Elevation	30°	50°	70°	90°
$\Delta_f = 15 \text{ KHz}$				
R_ϵ^{C2} (km)	3.22	2.27	1.88	1.74
$\Delta_f = 30 \text{ KHz}$				
R_ϵ^{C2} (km)	2.88	3.89	5.04	4.76
$\Delta_f = 60 \text{ KHz}$				
R_ϵ^{C2} (km)	1.44	1.93	3.68	10.73

TABLE III: Uncertainty region supported by the modified preamble C2 at the Ka band and in LEO constellations at 600km altitude

Elevation	30°	50°	70°	90°
$\Delta_f = 15 \text{ KHz}$				
R_ϵ^{C2} (km)	3.22	2.27	1.88	1.74
$\Delta_f = 30 \text{ KHz}$				
R_ϵ^{C2} (km)	8.59	6.05	5.04	4.76
$\Delta_f = 60 \text{ KHz}$				
R_ϵ^{C2} (km)	5.76	7.81	11.32	10.73

angles. Following this methodology, we conducted assessments in various scenarios at the Ka band. For instance, when $R_\epsilon = 1\text{km}$, the system can effectively handle the maximum TO and CFO values with $\Delta_f = 15, 30, 60\text{KHz}$. However, as the error margin expands to $R_\epsilon = 2.5\text{km}$, only the configuration with $\Delta_f = 30 \text{ KHz}$ remains viable. In the most challenging scenario, where $R_\epsilon = 5\text{km}$, none of the SCS configurations enable successful uplink synchronization. To provide the desired robustness, we propose to modify the random access signal. The new design principles are addressed in the next section.

III. PREAMBLE DESIGN

The new design is built upon the preamble format C2 with the objective of estimating long delays in the Ka band [10]. The enhancement is based on modifying the preamble sequence and increasing the length of the CP by a factor of N . Thus, $T_{CP} = 66.66 \times 2^{-\mu} \times N \mu s$, for $\mu = 0, 1, 2$. This adaptation increase the robustness of the system to positioning errors. Following the same methodology outlined in Section II, the findings are presented in Table III. The C2 modified version has been generated with $N = 4$. For $\Delta_f = 15\text{KHz}$, the limiting factor is the CFO rather than the TO. This trend persists also at high elevation angles for $\Delta_f = 30, 60 \text{ KHz}$. Consequently, extending the CP does not yield noticeable improvements in certain configurations. An important finding is that uplink synchronization can be attained for $R_\epsilon \leq 5.76\text{Km}$ and $\Delta_f = 60\text{KHz}$, as long as the elevation angles is above 30°.

A. Preamble design principles

The preamble is not obtained by the conventional approach of repeating the ZC sequences as adopted in the standard. Rather, as detailed in [7], the extended sequence is generated by concatenating a single root ZC sequence with N differ-

Fig. 3: Preamble generation and detection method for localized CP mapping

ent cyclic shifts. Mathematically, the j -th sequence can be expressed using this matrix notation

$$\mathbf{s}_j = [x_{u,jCS}(0), \dots, x_{u,jCS}(N_{ZC} - 1)]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ZC} \times 1}, \quad (3)$$

for $j = 0, \dots, N - 1$. The cyclic shift CS is picked from the set $\{0, \dots, \lfloor N_{ZC}/(N - 1) \rfloor\}$. Let $x_{u,v}(n)$ denote the ZC sequence of length N_{ZC} that is generated after cyclically shifting by v positions the root sequence $x_u(n) = e^{j \frac{\pi u n(n+1)}{N_{ZC}}}$. For $u = 1, \dots, N_{ZC} - 1$, we define

$$x_{u,v}(n) = x_u((n+v)_{N_{ZC}}), \quad 0 \leq n \leq N_{ZC} - 1. \quad (4)$$

Let $(\cdot)_M$ denote modulo M operation. The original design appends all the CP blocks at the beginning of the burst, as Figure 3 shows. To generate the random access signal, each preamble is fed into the multicarrier modulator, which implements the discrete Fourier transform spread orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (DFT-s-OFDM) waveform. At reception, upon discarding the CP, a fixed detection window is used to capture all the preambles. Then, the samples are divided into N sequences that are processed by the multicarrier demodulator. The j -th demodulated sequence is represented by $y_j[n]$, for $n = 0, \dots, N_{ZC} - 1$. Owing to the delay and the CP transmission, the received sequence exhibits circularity. In general, $y_j[n]$ does not convey $x_{u,jCS}(n)$, but has contribution from two different preambles. Notice that the delay, which results from the imperfect compensation, is decomposed as the sum of its integer and fractional parts, yielding $\tau_T = \tau_I + \tau_f$. From the block diagram it can be inferred that τ_T is expressed in samples. For the sake of the analytical tractability, we initially set the sampling frequency to $f_s = N_{ZC} \Delta_f$. Based on this assumption, we can express the two delay components as $\tau_I = \lfloor \tau_T / N_{ZC} \rfloor N_{ZC}$ and $\tau_f = (\tau_T)_{N_{ZC}}$.

The proposed novelty at the transmitter stems from interleaving the CP blocks with the sequences. The concept is represented in Figure 4. At reception, N distributed CP blocks are discarded according to the transmission pattern. The resulting samples that are collected in the m -th window are demodulated, yielding $\{y_{m,0}[n], \dots, y_{m,N-1}[n]\}$. It deserves to be mentioned that the detection window needs to be shifted with steps of size N_{ZC} samples. This sliding window method ensures that preambles can be localized even if $N_{ZC} \leq \tau_T$. This means that the detector needs to be executed $N_w = \lfloor \tau_{\max} / N_{ZC} \rfloor$ times, where τ_{\max} is the maximum possible

Fig. 4: Preamble generation and detection method for distributed CP mapping

delay. It is worth mentioning that when the window is correctly placed, $y_{m,j}[n]$ is a circularly shifted version of $x_{u,jCS}(n)$. This is the key aspect to improve the performance of the detector with respect to [7]. An in-depth description of the detector is provided in Sections IV and V.

B. Preamble set

In the most general case, a single root index u is used to generate L preambles where each preamble is identified by the tuple (u, CS_l) , for $l = 0, \dots, L - 1$. The design constraints of $\{CS_0, \dots, CS_{L-1}\}$ are provided in [7].

IV. FRACTIONAL DELAY ESTIMATION

The detection schemes that allow the gNB to estimate the delay follow a two-step approach, where fractional and integer parts of the delay are separately estimated. This section focuses the attention on the estimation of τ_f . The estimation algorithm depends on the structure of the preamble. On the basis of the CP location, two designs are introduced. In both cases, we consider that at a given random access occasion, the user can pick any cyclic shift from a set that is formed by L elements. That is, $CS \in \{CS_0, \dots, CS_{L-1}\}$.

A. Localized CP mapping

First, we analyze the solution depicted in Figure 3, which is tailored to PRACH signals that allocate the CP blocks in contiguous time slots. The schematic view of the receiver highlights that the sequences $\{y_j[n]\}$ are formed by two preamble sequences. To find the signature of the received signal, all sequences are added to obtain $y_T[n] = \sum_j y_j[n]$. Neglecting the CFO, the signal that results from the combination can be expressed in a matrix form as

$$\mathbf{y}_T = h \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \mathbf{A}_{\tau_f} \mathbf{s}_j + \boldsymbol{\omega}_T, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_T = [y_T[0], \dots, y_T[N_{ZC} - 1]]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ZC} \times 1}$. The cyclic shift that is induced by τ_f is represented by the permutation matrix defined by

$$\mathbf{A}_m = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{m \times N_{ZC} - m} & \mathbf{I}_m \\ \mathbf{I}_{N_{ZC} - m} & \mathbf{0}_{N_{ZC} - m \times m} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ZC} \times N_{ZC}}, \quad (6)$$

for $m = 0, \dots, N_{ZC} - 1$. An interesting property is that the multiplication of two permutation matrices results in another

permutation matrix, i.e., $\mathbf{A}_{m_1}\mathbf{A}_{m_2} = \mathbf{A}_{(m_1+m_2)N_{ZC}}$. Using the matrix notation, (3) can be compactly written as

$$\mathbf{s}_j = \mathbf{A}_{N_{ZC}-jCS}\mathbf{x}_u, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_u = [x_u(0), \dots, x_u(N_{ZC}-1)]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ZC} \times 1}$. The channel coefficient is formulated as

$$h = \sqrt{\frac{G_R G_T}{P_L K_B T B}} e^{j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d_{\text{SAT-UE}}}. \quad (8)$$

The same model proposed in [12] is adopted. The magnitude of the channel is formulated as a function of the satellite antenna gain G_T , the UE antenna gain G_R , the path loss P_L , the Boltzmann constant K_B , the bandwidth B and the system noise temperature T . The satellite antenna gain is assumed to be constant over the uncertainty region. The phase term depends on the carrier wavelength λ and the slant range $d_{\text{SAT-UE}}$. Since the channel is normalized to the noise variance, the noise samples at the input of the receiver are modelled as circularly symmetric complex Gaussian random variables with zero mean and unit variance. Under this premise, it follows that $\boldsymbol{\omega}_T \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}_{N_{ZC} \times N_{ZC}}, N\mathbf{I}_{N_{ZC}})$. The variance of the additive term at the input of the detector is increased by a factor N , as a result of accumulating N sequences.

To estimate the delay, the detector first obtains the decision variable by computing the correlation between the received signal and a local sequence generated from the root ν , namely,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\nu\mu} &= \left| \mathbf{x}_\nu^H \mathbf{A}_{N_{ZC}-\mu}^H \mathbf{Y}_T / N_{ZC} \right|^2 \\ &= \left| \frac{h}{N_{ZC}} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \mathbf{x}_\nu^H \mathbf{A}_{(\tau_f-jCS-\mu)N_{ZC}} \mathbf{x}_u + \omega_{\nu\mu} \right|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

for $\nu = 1, \dots, N_{ZC} - 1$. As demonstrated in [12], the correlation is equivalent to applying the matched filter and the inverse DFT (IDFT). However, to ease the exposition, we stick to the direct implementation. Regardless of the implementation method, the correlation will exhibit N peaks located at $(\nu, \mu) = (u, \mu_j)$, where

$$\mu_j = (\tau_f - jCS)_{N_{ZC}}, \quad j = 0, \dots, N-1. \quad (10)$$

Hence, by detecting N correlation peaks equally spaced CS positions, it is straightforward to estimate τ_f from μ_0 .

It is worth emphasizing that only the correlation values that exceed a predefined threshold are classified as peak values. The peak search is executed in the subset that satisfies $\rho_{\nu\mu} \geq r_{\text{th}}^L$. Considering the guidelines reported in [7] and [12], the threshold is fully characterized by the chi-square distribution with two degrees of freedom and the target false alarm probability as follows

$$P_{\text{FA}} = 1 - \left(1 - e^{-\left(r_{\text{th}}^L \times \frac{N_{ZC}}{2N}\right)} \right)^{N_{ZC}}. \quad (11)$$

B. Distributed CP mapping

The alternative method represented in Figure 4 is based on allocating the CP blocks in non-contiguous time slots. Assum-

ing that the detection window m contains all the preambles, each sequence can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{y}_{mj} = h\mathbf{A}_{\tau_f}\mathbf{s}_j + \boldsymbol{\omega}_{mj}, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_{mj} = [y_{m,j}[0], \dots, y_{m,j}[N_{ZC}-1]]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ZC} \times 1}$. In alignment with the model defined in Section IV-A, the noise vector follows this distribution $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{mj} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}_{N_{ZC} \times N_{ZC}}, \mathbf{I}_{N_{ZC}})$. To detect the preamble, each sequence is correlated with a candidate preamble, leading to

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{\nu\mu}^{mj} &= \left| \mathbf{x}_\nu^H \mathbf{A}_{N_{ZC}-\mu}^H \mathbf{y}_{mj} / N_{ZC} \right|^2 \\ &= \left| \frac{h}{N_{ZC}} \mathbf{x}_\nu^H \mathbf{A}_{(\tau_f-jCS-\mu)N_{ZC}} \mathbf{x}_u + \omega_{\nu\mu}^{mj} \right|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Bearing this expression in mind, one can find that the peak of $\gamma_{\nu\mu}^{mj}$ is located at the grid-point $(\nu, \mu) = (u, \mu_j)$. The variable μ_j is formulated in (10). To enhance the detection, we can compute a new decision variable, namely,

$$\rho_{\nu\mu}^{CS} = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \gamma_{\nu(\mu+jCS)}^{mj}. \quad (14)$$

The non-coherent summation that is performed in (14) is fundamental to improve the performance of the detector with respect to the design presented in Section IV-A. One of the benefits is that the search procedure is simplified, as the delay τ_f can be estimated from a single peak that is located at $(\nu, \mu) = (u, \mu_0)$. Another advantage is that the peak level in (14) increases with N . By contrast, the magnitude of the peaks in (9) is invariant with N .

The methodology to identify the peaks again is based on selecting the correlation values that exceed the detection threshold, i.e.,

$$\rho_{\nu\mu}^{CS} \geq r_{\text{th}}^D. \quad (15)$$

Since the noise component in (14) features a chi-square distribution with $2N$ degrees of freedom, the false alarm probability and the threshold are related as follows

$$P_{\text{FA}} = 1 - \left(1 - e^{-\left(r_{\text{th}}^D \times \frac{N_{ZC}}{2}\right)} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{1}{j!} \left(r_{\text{th}}^D \times \frac{N_{ZC}}{2} \right)^j \right)^{N_{ZC}}. \quad (16)$$

It is worth emphasizing that when the window is not correctly placed, the demodulated sequences do not capture all the samples of the preamble. Accordingly, some of the variables that are used to determine the peak location in (14), may just have contribution from the noise. In spite of this, (15) may be satisfied. To eliminate the false peak in this undesired situation, an additional test is deemed necessary. In (14), the detector only considers the variables that satisfy

$$\gamma_{\nu(\mu+jCS)}^{mj} \geq r_{\text{th},2}^D. \quad (17)$$

This has been proven to be an effective criterion to improve the performance of the detector. The second threshold $r_{\text{th},2}^D$ is formulated as function of the false alarm probability as

$$P_{\text{FA}} = 1 - \left(1 - \left(e^{-\left(r_{\text{th},2}^D \times \frac{N_{ZC}}{2}\right)} \right)^N \right)^{N_{ZC}}. \quad (18)$$

This expression defines the error case where no preamble is transmitted and (17) holds true.

V. INTEGER DELAY ESTIMATION

This section describes the procedure to estimate the integer delay in the distributed mapping approach. For the localized counterpart, we address the reader to [7].

Upon performing the search procedure, if a single correlation peak is obtained in the m -th window, then we can resolve that the integer delay is $\tau_I = mN_{ZC}$. However, difficulties are encountered when multiple peaks emerge in different windows. To resolve the ambiguity, the signature of each detected peak is defined. To differentiate the candidates, the k -th correlation peak is identified by the tuple $\mathcal{S}_k = \{u_k, N_{CS_k}, w_k, \mu_0^k, \dots, \mu_{N-1}^k\}$ where u_k denotes the root index, N_{CS_k} denotes the cyclic shift and w_k denotes the detection window index. The indexes $\{\mu_0^k, \dots, \mu_{N-1}^k\}$ correspond to the pattern of the detected preamble. In this regard, μ_0^k corresponds to the estimated fractional delay τ_f^k . The rest of the indexes are generated according to (10), i.e., $\mu_j^k = \left(\tau_f^k - jN_{CS_k}\right)_{N_{ZC}}$.

In the following, we develop strategies to detect and correct the errors when two peaks are associated to the same preamble sequence. The candidates are labelled by \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 . The two sets differ in the window index and share the same root index and the cyclic shift, i.e., $w_1 \neq w_2$, $u_1 = u_2 = u$ and $N_{CS_1} = N_{CS_2} = CS$. The rest of entries might be different. Without loss of generality, the correct and the false peaks are represented by \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 , respectively.

A. Error detection in single-user communications

In this case, a single user is active and the preamble is detected in adjacent windows. That is, $|w_1 - w_2| = 1$. In the window w_2 , which is not correctly placed, the demodulated sequences $\{y_{w_2,j}[n]\}$ will have contribution of the ZC sequences. Thus, a portion of the ZC sequences will be present in addition to the noise term. This circumstance renders ineffective the test in (17) for identifying false peaks. Under these circumstances, the decision to estimate the integer delay will be based on finding the boundaries of the received burst. This is tantamount to computing the cross-correlation measurement $S_k = S_k^0 + S_k^{N-1}$, where

$$S_k^j = \left| \sum_{n=0}^{N_{ZC}-1} x_{u,jCS}^*(n) y_{w_k,j}(n + \tau_f^k) \right|^2 + \left| \sum_{n=0}^{N_{ZC}-1} x_{u,jCS}^*(n) y_{w_k,j}(n + \tau_f^k + N_{ZC}) \right|^2. \quad (19)$$

The sequences $y_{w_1,j}(n + \tau_f^1)$ and $y_{w_1,j}(n + \tau_f^1 + N_{ZC})$ integrate a complete ZC sequence. Notice that one of the sequences corresponds to the CP block. In the adjacent window w_2 , either $y_{w_2,j}(n + \tau_f^2)$ or $y_{w_2,j}(n + \tau_f^2 + N_{ZC})$, will be formed by noise samples or by a preamble that is orthogonal to $x_{u,jCS}(n)$. As a consequence, the cross-correlation value will be significantly decreased. This observation highlights that the estimation of

TABLE IV: System parameters

PRACH bandwidth	$B_{\text{PRACH}} = 8.34\text{MHz}$
System bandwidth	$B = 400\text{MHz}$
Sequence duration	$T_{\text{SEQ}} = 16.67 \text{ us}$
UE antenna gain	$G_T = 43.2 \text{ dBi}$
Satellite antenna G/T	$G_R/T = 5 \text{ dB K}^{-1}$
Beam diameter	50 km
Satellite altitude	600 km
Minimum elevation angle	30°

the integer delay could be governed by S_k . In this regard, we propose to select the window index that exhibits the highest cross-correlation measurement.

Interestingly, in some cases, the decision could be taken without making any additional computation. More precisely, for small (large) τ_f , we can deduce that a significant amount of preamble samples will be located at the window preceding (following) the correct detection window. Under this premise, the correct integer delay will be associated to the highest (lowest) window index for small (large) τ_f . To apply these rules, we consider $\tau_f < \tau_\epsilon$ and $N_{ZC} - \tau_f < \tau_\epsilon$ to determine if τ_f is either small or large. Note that the larger the τ_ϵ , the higher the computational saving. In this sense, it has been experimentally verified that τ_ϵ can be up to $N_{ZC}/4$ and still accurate integer delay estimations are obtained, without relying on S_k .

B. Error detection in multi-user communications

Up to this point, we have described the sources of error that stem from the leakage of the preambles through adjacent windows. Another foreseeable error is related to the reuse of the root indexes. By design, a single root ZC sequence generates L preamble sequences. A very detrimental situation is created when multiple preambles that share the same root index are simultaneously received in the same random access occasion. In the worst case scenario, there are L active users. Thanks to the decision variable introduced in (14) and the tests defined in (15) and (17), we can recognize the patterns, which allows us to distinguish the preambles. It is important to remark that as L increases, the probability to find a valid signature that results from the combination of the received preambles increases. This problems also affects the random access signal based on the localized CP mapping. However, no specific solution is presented in [7]. As an enhancement, we propose to take some measures to identify the false peaks. Imagine that the search procedure yields these signatures $\mathcal{S}_1, \dots, \mathcal{S}_{L_T}$, for $L_T > 2$. To declare that \mathcal{S}_k is a valid sequence, the detector verifies if the set $\{\mu_0^k, \dots, \mu_{N-1}^k\}$ is included in $\bigcup_{l \neq k} \{\mu_0^l, \dots, \mu_{N-1}^l\}$. If so, the peak is discarded. To reduce the complexity, it is advisable to relax the root index reuse, which boils down to selecting a small L .

VI. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The localized and the distributed mapping approaches are compared in this section. The system parameters are gathered in Table IV. The modified preamble C2 is implemented with $\Delta_f = 60\text{KHz}$, $N_{ZC} = 139$ and $N_w = N = 4$. According to

Fig. 5: Contour of the differential delay in μs .

Fig. 6: Contour of the differential Doppler frequency shift in KHz.

the analysis conducted in Section II, this design is able to handle the TO and the CFO that stem from the positioning errors at the Ka band. In Figure 5, we have depicted the contour of the differential delay when the radius of the uncertainty region is $R_\epsilon = 5\text{Km}$. As expected, when the elevation angle is 90° , the differential delay is almost negligible. Conversely, for 30° , the magnitude of the delays is significantly increased. If we draw the attention to the Doppler effects, Figure 6 reveals that the highest frequency shifts are experienced at 90° .

Concerning the preamble generation, each single root index is used to generate $L = 2$ preambles. Following the design guidelines reported in [7], the users can pick the cyclic shift as $CS \in \{23, 29\}$.

In Figure 7, we compute the missed detection probability (MDP) when the positioning error is uniformly distributed inside an uncertainty region of $R_\epsilon = 5\text{km}$. As a result, the magnitude of time and frequency offsets is dictated by Figures 5 and 6. The error cases resulting in incorrect detection encompass several possibilities: 1) Detecting a preamble different from the one transmitted, 2) Failing to detect any preamble at all, and 3) Correctly detecting the preamble but with an erroneous timing estimation. Specifically, a timing estimation error is flagged if the magnitude of the error exceeds $1/(N_{ZC} \times \Delta_f)$. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is formulated as $SNR = |h|^2 P$, where P is the transmit power. The number of simultaneous users is denoted as N_U and the elevation angle as θ . The thresholds defined in Section IV and V are computed to ensure a false alarm probability of $P_{FA} = 10^{-3}$.

The numerical results verify that the distributed approach

Fig. 7: MDP versus SNR

achieves the best performance. Similar results are obtained with low and high elevation angles. The key aspect of the distributed scheme is the non-coherent accumulation that is performed in (14). The plots also highlight that 2 users can be successively detected on the same random access occasion, reusing the same root index. As expected, by increasing the number of users, the performance of the detector degrades. The localized approach provides similar results with one and two users. Hence, for the clarity in the presentation only the case $N_U = 1$ has been represented.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have investigated the RA procedure to allow direct LEO satellite access at the Ka band. As an enhancement, we have introduced a novel design for the PRACH signal and its detection scheme. The proposed solution centers around the modification of the preamble format C2, as specified in 5G NR air interface. The new PRACH signal entails extending the CP and concatenating a single root ZC sequence with various cyclic shifts. Furthermore, it involves interleaving the CP blocks with the ZC sequences. The modifications enable the gNB to detect the preamble even in the presence of TO and CFO values that are not supported by the standard. Concerning the application scope, this redesigned PRACH signal is particularly well-suited to scenarios where the UE's location is prone to errors. Our numerical simulations demonstrate that the preamble can be reliably detected even in the presence of positioning uncertainties of up to 5 km. Future work may consider developing more efficient algorithms for preamble detection and may analyse the impact of satellite positioning errors on the MDP.

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